

Deliverable D13.2

Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

Project Title (Grant agreement number)	EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement 101131056		
Project Acronym (EC call)	EOSC-ENTRUST		
WP No & Title	WP13: Trusted research environment blueprint - Establishing a common terminology and approach		
WP Leaders	Miikka Kallberg (CSC), Pål Sætrom (NTNU)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	2. CSC, 12. UiB		
Contractual delivery date	30/11/2024	Actual delivery date	29/11/2024
Delayed	No		
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1. Executive Summary

The overarching goal of the EOSC-ENTRUST training package is to support organisations with existing and emerging TREs in onboarding the EOSC-ENTRUST network and federation. The training package will also provide guidelines and tutorials on how researchers and others best may use the services offered by the participating TREs and what is expected of them in return.

This deliverable represents the first version of the training materials for building interoperable TRE services according to the year one version of the EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework, which is presented in Deliverable D13.4, also due on 30th November 2024. In this version, we have identified individuals who will be involved in governing, operating and/or using emerging and existing TREs and mapped their training needs. We have then structured these needs into related topics that will be further developed and described along with the maturation of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint itself. Finally, we present an initial list of existing training material on sensitive data and TREs that could be useful for these individuals.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP4, WP5)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP2, WP3)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP2) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP2, WP5)	Yes
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP6)	Yes

	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP6)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP4, WP5).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP4)	Yes
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP5)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP4).	Yes
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP5)	Yes
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP4, WP5).	Yes
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP4, WP5).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP2, WP4) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP3).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1, WP2).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

selected transnational programmes		
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1, WP2).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP2).</p>	No
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP4).</p>	No
	<p>4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP3)</p>	No

3. Methods

3.1 Scope of Deliverable

In this first edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package, we present a structured overview of the training needs of a range of actors expected to interact with the resulting EOSC-ENTRUST federation and network. We also present an initial list of existing training material on sensitive data and TREs that could be useful for these actors.

Larger parts of our efforts have so far centred around understanding what different representatives from an organisation hosting a TRE need to learn in order to successfully build, adjust and onboard their TRE to the network, but we have also covered other actors

involved, such as organisations providing data that may ultimately be shared through the network and users of the TREs. This deliverable will be followed by an updated and further developed version after year two of the project, and ultimately by the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package as an online guide that effectively points the reader to the topics that are relevant to them after the third and final year.

We have chosen to design Personas to help us identify a useful range of training topics for individuals who will be involved in governing, operating and/or using emerging and existing TREs that intend to join the EOSC-ENTRUST federated network. Learner Personas are fictional characters that reflect characteristics of the audience being trained. The Personas may represent their goals, skills, attitudes and behaviours and their personification helps us target their training needs more precisely. The Personas presented in this document are built on the joint experience of all contributors to this deliverable, who in one way or another have filled most of the roles we foresee will interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST network.

3.2 Relationships with other WPs and deliverables

This deliverable is tightly linked to D13.4 that describes the first edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and Interoperability format. The architecture and recommendations there will greatly influence the specific content of the training package outlined in the present deliverable, but as the first edition of this Blueprint is developed in parallel with the Training package, these details will naturally be clearer in the next phase of the project. The learner Personas and topics have been developed with input and contributions from members of all WPs in the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

3.3 Methodology

The EOSC-ENTRUST Personas and their training needs were designed through a series of meetings and creative workshops open to all project participants.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Developing the EOSC-ENTRUST Personas

We identified the personas by conducting a literature review of existing work, and referenced the DARE UK Federated Blueprint Architecture², focusing particularly on [section 3.2](#) (User Persona Development: Federation Roles and Actors) and [section 3.2.5](#) (User Personas). Additionally, we referenced roles identified in SATRE specification³.

² <https://docs.google.com/document/d/17RjaSsudziwq6Af3910ji50risVdUXgO/edit#heading=h.uwcbttowwrl>

³ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/latest/roles.html>

We agreed that the following roles are most likely to interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST network and thereby benefit from our training:

- TRE Owner - the person legally responsible for the TRE
This role corresponds to SATRE's Top Management. Both represent leadership roles responsible for governance and strategic decision-making within the TRE environment. The TRE Owner is responsible for understanding both national and international legal frameworks, which aligns well with SATRE's emphasis on governance and risk ownership.
- TRE Builder - e.g. a systems developer or -architect
This role corresponds to SATRE's Builder, Developer and Database Administrator. The proposed personas here include individuals responsible for building and operating TREs.
Gaps: SATRE roles do not explicitly differentiate between different experience levels, while we distinguish between new and experienced TRE builders and propose different training needs based on expertise.
- TRE Operator - e.g. a system administrator
This role corresponds to SATRE's Operator, particularly in managing infrastructure and ensuring compliance with security standards.
Gaps: Cross-border legal requirements and GDPR compliance is not emphasised in SATRE's Operator role, topics we find relevant also for this role..
- TRE User - e.g. a researcher
This role corresponds to SATRE's Data Analyst, focusing on data analysis and learning to navigate TREs under supervision. Both roles require understanding how to work within a TRE, including data import and export processes.
- TRE Federation operator - the person overseeing the services connecting the TREs
- Data provider - the person responsible for the data being shared through the TRE.
This role corresponds to SATRE's Information Asset Owner and Data Steward. The emphasis is on data quality, compliance, and data security policies, including encryption and secure transfer of data.

To understand the Personas, where they come from and how they see TREs and the EOSC-ENTRUST network, we found it useful to picture their following characteristics:

- Name
- Professional role - related to TREs
- Short bio - what experience are they carrying with them?
- Goals: What are they trying to do? "I want to do X so that I can achieve Y"
- Pain points: What is stopping them from doing X? What are their worries, concerns, difficulties, barriers related to TREs?
- Key motivations for being involved with TREs and EOSC-ENTRUST
- Training needs

- Optimal training format: online guide, short videos, training course

A final intensive and creative workshop among direct deliverable contributors resulted in eight EOSC-ENTRUST Personas presented in detail in Appendix 1, with training needs further analysed in section 4.2 below.

4.2 Analysis of the EOSC-ENTRUST Persona training needs

The collective training needs of the EOSC-ENTRUST Personas are summarised in Table 1.

The training needs outlined in the table were identified through a structured methodology that involved direct discussions with key stakeholders⁴. Specifically, we conducted zoom meetings and a workshop-style discussion with subject matter experts and stakeholders representing some of the mentioned personas. During this session we gathered feedback and insights on the specific skills and formal qualifications needed for each role. This collaborative approach allowed us to capture real-world training needs that are as relevant to these roles as possible.

*Table 1. Training needs of EOSC-ENTRUST Personas**

Role	Training needs and -material
TRE Owner (Maria)	National and international legal frameworks influencing the federation Governance model of the federation and its implications for her organisation Basic principles of a TRE
TRE Builder and Operator** (Bob, Zara and Tom)	TRE zones and functionality TRE requirements and compliance Information security Encryption, secure transfer protocols, and measures for data anonymization Benefits of the federation Introduction to the federated system. Standards for interoperability Security best practices.

⁴

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qu92OCuJ_I0luS08bDkuoKZ1o5k8iv8o_KKgzzQjwAQ/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.sgbfxt h2v0ix

	Legal requirements for cross-border data sharing
Federation operator (Roy)	Federation common technical service platform. Cybersecurity, especially network security. Regulatory and accreditation frameworks - GDPR, ISO27001, NIS2
Data provider (Anna)	Legal frameworks GDPR requirements / data protection laws Data security policies, including encryption, secure transfer protocols, and measures for data anonymization How to work within TREs
TRE User*** (Dana and Carlos)	How to work within a TRE; access, navigation, import/export, restrictions National and international legislations governing the use and share of data. Responsibilities and limitations connected to data shared to them by others PI responsibilities (legal and ethical) - what may happen to the data that they share?

* see Appendix 1 for description of all EOSC-ENTRUST Personas

** both junior and experienced

*** both PI and junior researcher

The EOSC-ENTRUST Personas have quite different paths leading into the EOSC-ENTRUST network, but we tried to consolidate and summarise their training needs outlined in Table 1 and Appendix 1 into a number of topics they would benefit from covering to varying degrees, see Table 2:

Table 2. Topics to be covered in the EOSC-ENTRUST training package

Section	Topics
Introduction	<p>What is the EOSC-ENTRUST federation and what is it trying to accomplish?</p> <p>What is a TRE?</p> <p>Why should a TRE join the federation, and what are the potential consequences?</p> <p>What steps does a TRE need to follow in order to join the federation?</p> <p>What are the requirements?</p>
Legal frameworks	<p>International legislations influencing the federation and the onboarding TREs (with a note that each country may have additional national legislations that may further influence the onboarding journey)</p> <p>GDPR, EHDS, NIS2, Data Governance Act, Interoperable Europe Act</p>
Governance model	<p>Who can agree that a TRE and its data joins the network?</p> <p>Who can approve that access to data stored in the TRE can be shared?</p> <p>Who approves that a TRE fulfils minimum regulatory requirements?</p> <p>What legal entities can represent a node?</p> <p>Sanctions upon possible misconduct</p>
Building and operating an EOSC-ENTRUST-compliant TRE	<p>Zones and components constituting a TRE</p> <p>Information security; encryption, secure transfer protocols, and measures for data anonymization</p> <p>Minimum requirements and compliance</p> <p>Federation platform - standards and interoperability</p> <p>Technical parameters for different protocols to be interoperable, how to align your TRE</p> <p>Onboarding journey in detail</p>

User guide	How to work within a TRE; access, navigation, import/export, restrictions, obligations Possible user certification or passport Data management?
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4.3 Existing training material for TREs

We gathered an initial list of existing training material on sensitive data and TREs by reaching out to the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider forum for relevant onboarding and training material. We further conducted a web search on topics such as ‘analysis of sensitive data’ and ‘TRE onboarding’. The resulting material is gathered in a live form within the EOSC-ENTRUST project area⁵ and also listed in Appendix 2. Currently, we have identified more material targeting TRE users than TRE providers.

5. Discussion and conclusions

A key challenge in the EOSC-ENTRUST project is the interdependency of deliverables both within and between work packages. Certain parts of the training catalogue, as well as the development of the training guide, require input from other WPs in the project, especially the Driver Forum and the Provider Forum. Further, sections of the training content that depend on the EOSC-ENTRUST Interoperability Format or specific components of the Blueprint being developed in parallel in Deliverable 13.3, cannot be fully completed until those elements are developed. Hence, this interdependence may delay the progress as we await both feedback from the stakeholders and completion of essential work packages. At this first phase of the project, we therefore chose to focus on understanding the Personas that would be interacting with the EOSC-ENTRUST federation and their training needs.

In conclusion, we have identified the audience for an initial structure and content of a training package to accompany the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and Interoperability Format. This package will guide actors eventually involved in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation to training material that is relevant for them, and ensure that they are fully equipped to perform their associated tasks. These tasks may include:

- Deciding if an institutional TRE should join the EOSC-ENTRUST network
- Building a TRE and onboarding it to the EOSC-ENTRUST network in compliance with the requirements
- Performing cutting-edge research on sensitive data across European borders

⁵ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1nLuqxNkNKVGnhCZBJA2cMxXHmH_gkE2-RWAp2csXPBA/edit?gid=0#gid=0

6. Next steps

In the second edition of this Deliverable, we will continue gathering material for a training catalogue based on the needs outlined by the Personas and consolidate this with the first edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and Interoperability format, which is being developed in parallel with this training package. We will continue to survey relevant platforms for material that could be helpful, such as user guides and staff onboarding material for individual TREs. We will further perform a gap analysis on the Personas to identify, for each of them, material that already exists and would be useful as well as material that would be useful but does not yet exist.

We plan to publish this catalogue as an online guide in a branched structure as illustrated in Figure 1, in a style similar to related resources such as the FEGA onboarding guide⁶ and RDMKit⁷. This format will easily allow the Personas and real life trainees to identify topics that are relevant for them, and to go in depth in these at their own pace. We will use GitHub Pages and Markdown language to make the guide easily accessible, maintainable, and user-friendly.

Figure 1. Structure for the online guide that will constitute the EOSC-ENTRUST training package.

The resulting training catalogue will be a dynamic resource that gradually will grow from a collection of links to existing relevant material into a comprehensive guide to topics that are relevant to cover for individuals that will interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. We will further assign an editorial board to ensure that the resource is up to date with recent technological and legal developments.

⁶ <https://ega-archive.github.io/FEGA-onboarding/>

⁷ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

7. Impact

We have outlined a tentative pathway to outcomes and impact for the EOSC-ENTRUST Training Package, as shown in Table 3. At this early phase of the project, we believe that the greatest contribution of this deliverable will be to help pinpoint, clarify and thereby improve challenging sections in the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint itself. After the Training Package is published, we believe that this will greatly empower organisations hosting TREs to onboard the Federation, and also empower researchers to use the TRE network, have access to larger sets of data and potentially perform great science.

Table 3. Tentative impact pathway for the EOSC-ENTRUST Training Package

Activities (what was done)	Output (directly from activities)	Outcomes (from current deliverable)	Impact (longer term, after final version published)
Meetings and workshops with collaborative work to try to shape the Training Package that will accompany the EOSC-ENTRUST Architecture Blueprint	Personas that will interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST network and their training needs	<p>Empathy and understanding of Personas and their training needs</p> <p>Training needs are fed into the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and help pinpoint sections that are particularly challenging and ambiguous.</p> <p>Challenging Blueprint sections are further clarified and addressed in greater detail</p>	<p>TRE owners and operators are empowered to join the network and federation</p> <p>Researchers are empowered to use the TRE network</p> <p>Researchers have access to greater data sets and can perform high-impact research on sensitive data</p> <p>Scientific break-throughs are made in domains that have been hampered by privacy regulations earlier</p>

8. Appendix 1. Full list of Personas to address in the EOSC-ENTRUST training package

TRE owner

Name and role: Maria is the rector of a university that hosts the academic TRE. She is the academic head of the university and has the ultimate responsibility for and management of all activity at the university, including the TRE and its involvement in the EOSC-ENTRUST network.

Short bio: Maria is originally a professor of ancient literature and has never come across the need to protect her own research within a TRE. Her experience with IT and computing is limited beyond academic text processing and administrative systems. She has a good understanding of the programs and collaborations her university is involved in but has naturally delegated some of her responsibilities to the university director and IT-related responsibilities further to the IT director.

Goals: Maria's main commitment is to ensure that the university improves its level of excellence in science and education during her election period. She works passionately to make the university more attractive for funders, star researchers, and highly skilled students.

Pain points: Maria is responsible for the reputation of the university and will ultimately be the one to blame if there is a data breach. Her name and the university will then be all over the local, national and academic newspapers. All researchers affiliated with the university may as a result be temporarily banned from having access to national registry and population-level data. Maria is afraid of what this may do to the incoming funding streams and student numbers. Maria is also worried about the current and long-term costs accompanying the local EOSC-ENTRUST node, and wants to ensure that a model for sustainable operation is developed before her university joins. She is also wondering who will run the federation after the implementation phase is finished as she knows from experience that costly initiatives tend to die at this point.

Key motivations: Maria believes that hosting a local EOSC-ENTRUST node aligns well with her commitment to excellent science and education at her university. She further foresees that this may even lead to increased usage of the university TRE, and thereby more income for the university.

Training needs: Maria needs to understand the governance model of the Entrust network and federation and what this implies for her responsibilities as the TRE owner. She also needs to fully understand the legislation related to the federation and the implications of joining this federation for her university. What is she committing to? What can potentially

happen to the data that the researchers at her university are sharing through the federation? Maria further needs to have a basic understanding of what a TRE is and also what it is not. Her time is extremely limited and she therefore needs to find an effective way to be trained. She would possibly delegate this training to the university IT director, who can in turn fill her in on the things she needs to know. So in practice, she would receive her TRE-related training through meetings with them.

Training keywords: Local legal frameworks, GDPR, governance, risk assessment and compliance.

TRE builder: existing TRE

Name and role: Bob is a system developer at a long-established TRE hosting survey data on democratic elections. He was instrumental in building a pioneering TRE more than 10 years ago and still has the main responsibility for the architecture and interoperability of the system as it looks today.

Short bio: Bob graduated with a master's degree in computer science 20 years ago. Since then, he has been involved in several IT infrastructure projects in both the private and public sector, and has gradually specialised in data security and health care data. He has always been an advocate of collaborative work and is known for documenting his work carefully.

Goals: Bob's main professional goal for the last 10 years has been to build a secure and scalable TRE that ensures compliance with regulatory requirements and data protection laws and at the same time provides a good user experience. He continuously works to improve the service and adapt to the changing legal requirements.

Pain points: Bob's TRE has had no major security breach since its launch and he is very sceptical of all changes and integrations that increase the risk. He already finds it challenging enough to balance the need for data security with good user experience and is a bit stressed with the thought of adapting his perfect service to fit the federation

Key motivations: Bob is still motivated by the technical challenges that he expects will come along when connecting his TRE to the EOSC-ENTRUST network. He is also eager to contribute to changes that provide value to research.

Training needs: Bob needs to convince himself that the benefits of joining the federation outnumber the risks. He would benefit from an introduction to the federated system. He further needs to get on top of the documentation on the standards for interoperability and security best practices. He would further benefit from an introduction to the legal requirements for cross-border data sharing.

Training format: Bob prefers to do his training at his own pace, preferably through an online guide with links to material that will allow him to go more in-depth on the topics he finds particularly interesting.

Training keywords: Technical training on TRE technologies, system security, scalability, compliance requirements, infrastructure best practices, and SOP development. Legal frameworks to some degree

TRE builder: emerging TRE

Name and role: Zara is a system developer and has recently moved positions and is now in charge of building a TRE for the national genome centre, which will host and give qualified users access to its collection of clinical and research-based data.

Short bio: Zara has a degree in information technology with a specialisation in UX. Since her graduation, she has worked as a developer with a wide range of employers, from small start-ups to public offices. She has always paid special attention to the usability of the systems she has built and sees this as a strength in her new role, as TREs have a reputation for being a bit complicated to use.

Goals: Zara aims to build a TRE that both securely meets all requirements and is as intuitive in use as possible.

Pain points: Limited experience, Worried that user-friendliness is sacrificed over compliance with both TRE and federation requirements,

Key motivations: Give the operators and users a good experience

Training needs: Technical training on TRE technologies; compliance and meeting TRE requirements, TRE zones and functionality, info security, encryption, data flow, compliance, firewalls, scalability, infrastructure best practices, and SOP development. Legal frameworks to some degree, federation common technical service platform

TRE operator

Name and role: Tom manages the daily operation of a TRE developed at a private research institute. In his work, he embodies the role of both a builder and an operator, ensuring that standard operating procedures (SOPs) are meticulously followed, while also being flexible enough to tackle unexpected technical issues. His resilience and problem-solving skills make him a reliable team player and a formidable guardian of the TRE infrastructure.

Short bio: Tom has a degree in Computer Science from a high-ranking university known for its prestigious programs and influential alumni. In his previous career, he has worked for companies in the private sector, including a consulting company specialising in advising the public sector in reorganisation processes. His experience is mainly with Windows-based

systems, which fits well with the systems constituting the TRE he currently manages. Tom's personality is characterised by his attention to detail and commitment to operational excellence.

Goals: Tom aims to continue streamlining the operational processes within the TRE. He is keen on developing advanced troubleshooting protocols and enhancing the ethical guidelines that govern the system. By continuously updating his knowledge of compliance and security maintenance practices, he aspires to create a more robust and secure research environment.

Pain points: Tom's greatest fear is users losing their data – whether it's through theft or accidental deletion. He is concerned about the potential risks associated with connecting his TRE to the other TREs in the EOSC-ENTRUST network and worries that by joining the federation it will be harder for him to protect the data from being breached or stolen. He also worries that he will not be able to keep up to date on his existing duties with the increased need to learn new technologies and their implications. Lastly, he is anxious that the federation will force him into Linux land, which he has not been actively using since his studies.

Key motivations: Tom's primary motivation is to contribute to a trusted and secure research ecosystem, which also extends to the solutions being developed for integrating multiple TREs in the EOSC-ENTRUST network. He is passionate about creating an environment where sensitive data can be handled safely and responsibly and will bring this perspective when adapting his TRE to the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. His drive comes from a deep-seated belief in the importance of ethical responsibility and operational integrity in the research domain. A key aspect of Tom's motivation is the desire to learn new things and having the opportunity, or even the requirement, to do so, as encouraged by the institution hosting his TRE. He sees that by helping connect his TRE to the EOSC-ENTRUST network he will be able to grow his technical skills significantly and at the same time keep his guarding hands on the data in his TRE in the process.

Training needs and format: Similar to Bob and Zara, the TRE builders. Operational procedures, troubleshooting, ethical guidelines, compliance, and security maintenance practices. Legal frameworks to some degree. Mainly online training as he does not have the time to take time off for training. Since he is also operating the TRE in addition to building it, he might need more training on federated TREs and legal frameworks.

Federation operator

Name and role: Roy is employed to operate the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. As such, he oversees the operation of a network of TREs, ensuring they work together efficiently and securely. Roy is responsible for running the common technical services that connect TREs and data services to form the federation, maintaining the integrity of the network, and

ensuring safety across the federated system. Roy's responsibility extends to all the security controls required by the overall federation governance, and he needs to ensure GDPR compliance across the network, among other regulations. Roy finds the role interesting, challenging and stressful in equal measure.

Short bio: Roy has a background in physics and distributed computing. While working on building large-scale computing platforms for high-energy physics data, the COVID-19 pandemic kick-started his interest in systems for sharing health and demographic data. Roy decided that using his skills to try to improve the systems for large-scale research in public health would be something really worth doing. Coming from academia, his infrastructure skillset is very open-source. He has had good and bad experiences with proprietary software, but the bad experiences have made him a little wary of vendor lock-in.

Goals:

- wants to help run the infrastructure to support more and better research with sensitive data at national and international scale.
- wants to ensure that running the infrastructure is as automated and streamlined as it can be.
- wants to support new and emerging analytical use-cases across the network to enable better science; *"I don't just want to run it, I want to help advance it!"*.
- wants to find ways to make research with sensitive data more transparent, to keep the public onside.

Pain points:

- worries about the software or platform vendor lock-in.
- worries about adding more complexity to TRE operations!
- worries about introducing single points of failure into the TRE network.
- hates getting involved in the higher-level politics of the federation governance!

Key motivations:

- Enabling better science at population-scale. We can do this!
- Keeping the public onside! We have to be honest and transparent in everything we do.
- Building for the future. This is a long-term thing, not just a bunch of projects.

Training needs: A thorough grounding in the chosen federation common technical service platform - he needs to know this stuff inside-out. Cybersecurity, especially network security. He needs to keep this up-to-date because the threats change daily! An overview at least of the regulatory and accreditation frameworks I need to be aware of -- GDPR, ISO27001, NIS2, perhaps.

Data provider

Name and role: Anna is a highly skilled Data Protection Officer with a background in law, information security, and compliance. Her role is to navigate complex privacy regulations, particularly around the relevant regulations and GDPR. Anna works as a public officer at the national statistics agency. In her role as a Data Provider, she supplies data to TREs for sensitive research purposes, such as tax evasion, upon request by and approval of researchers. Her role includes managing data from public registries, coordinating with other officers and researchers who collect data, and ensuring that information/data is handled according to ethical and legal requirements. Anna needs to ensure that the data hosted by the agency complies with relevant regulations and standards (e.g. the national Personal Data- and Health Research Acts and GDPR). She also collaborates with TREs available for the researchers requesting data with the agency, and needs to have an overview of sharing agreements at all times.

Short bio: Anna has a background as a public health researcher, with first-hand experience with working on her own research data within a TRE. After her third post doc, she secured a permanent position at the national statistics agency, where she has great use of her expertise on sensitive data and at the same time does not have to worry about her academic future.

Goals:

- To keep data from her agency safe
- Have an overview of the entire data lifecycle
- Ensure the integrity and quality of data
- Ensure that data is well-documented (schema)

Pain points:

- Ensuring that data are handled securely and ethically at all times.
- Maintaining trust with the data subjects
- Navigating complex data regulations

Key motivations: Anna is motivated by the potential of data, contributing to better policies, and a better world; *“I want to ensure my data is properly documented and maintained to support effective research outcomes.”*

Training needs and format:

- Comprehensive training on GDPR requirements and other data protection laws (pdf documents)
- Training on data security policies, including encryption, secure transfer protocols, and measures for data anonymisation (workshop)
- Effective data management practices (learning modules)

- Effective collaboration within TREs (workshop and course on architecture blueprints)
- Effective and transparent communication (learning modules, Harvard Online)

Data sharing agreements, ethical data use, data quality standards, security requirements, and understanding of TRE processes.

TRE user: Principal investigator

Name and role: Dana is a professor at the Institute of Computer Science. At the University, Dana leads a small research team. Dana has the major responsibility for the data being managed within her group. She is also responsible for ensuring all internal processes are good and that there is no mistrust regarding her group's management of sensitive data. Dana has pyramidal responsibility and as such managerial responsibility for her team's actions. She needs to ensure that she and her team are properly trained in:

- making a project account and accessing the TRE, preferably with SSO
- requesting and ingesting data from the data provider
- requesting access to this data for herself and her team
- what tools are available for her computations
- how the generated computations must be handled
- possible restrictions on taking out the results for publications
- ensuring that her team members are following protocols

Short bio: Dana's research interests are in signal and image processing and machine learning. The team mainly conducts research on rare cancers, using image recognition to identify these cancers at an early stage. Her group is currently participating in two EU projects and one national-level project.

Goals: Dana is primarily focused on deliverables to the projects she is leading, ensuring quality research, and that her PhD candidates complete their PhDs. Dana needs to ensure that her team has access to the data (images of rare cancers) they need to train their models. As this data is sensitive, she needs to ensure it is handled correctly. Additionally, as these are high-resolution images, she needs a relatively large storage capacity and computing resources.

Pain points: Using the TRE should be an enabler of research, not a hindrance. Dana's team is made up of computer scientists as well as medical professionals. Therefore, the level of IT competence varies greatly. The training must accommodate a lower threshold of IT knowledge. Dana's team generally has varying knowledge of working with sensitive data and therefore the training must be clear as to what is and what is not allowed. This includes ethical and legal guidelines and regulations that must be followed, any data agreements concerning handling or transfer, etc

Training requirements: Ideally what she would like would be a mapped out and easy-to-follow process her team members can follow.

- Generally how a TRE works (concerning setting up a Data Management Plan)
- Responsibilities (including legal and ethical) as a PI
- Team accountability, compliance training, and risk management
- TRE access, account setup and navigation
- Access to data, either data already in the TRE or moving data into the TRE
- Restrictions on how to handle/what can be done with the results (publications)
- Data management,
- Benefits of the TRE federation

TRE user: Junior researcher

Name and role: Carlos is doing a PhD in human genomics in partnership with a private company that does genetic analysis. He needs to analyse and handle large amounts of sensitive data in a secure manner and must learn how to best conduct his research within a TRE in parallel with learning all the computational methods that will help him achieve his hopefully groundbreaking results. Carlos has some notion of Data Management, but still struggles to keep everything organised.

Goals: Carlos wants to compare the data from their clients with data from public databases without risking compromising their privacy. He further wants to expand the types of analysis he can do on the data.

Pain points: Carlos is quite inexperienced in using servers or working with the terminal, and feels that being forced to work remotely within an enclosed analysis environment greatly limits his research. Also, he lacks clear guidelines on what he is allowed to do and not do as a PhD student (academically) and as an analyst at the company. Also, there is some scepticism about sharing data within the private company that he is working in.

Key motivation: Carlos wants a system that can make his life easier by saving time in the analysis, organising all his data and making privacy protection easier. He is beginning to understand that the EOSC-ENTRUST network may help his research because he will have access to a larger collection of patient data.

Training needs: Carlos needs introductory training on how to efficiently connect to and use a TRE. He further needs training on GDPR and data privacy topics from a data processor / data analyst point of view. He would also benefit from training on Research Data Management within a closed environment and how to adapt FAIR principles to sensitive data. He aims to analyse data from multiple sources and domains, so an introduction to cross-domain data integration and the EOSC-ENTRUST federation will be useful, as well as the underlying legislations, ethical use of data and privacy awareness.

9. Appendix 2. Existing training material on TREs

No	Description of training material	Target Personas	Link
1	TeSS collection - RDMbites: Sensitive data	All	https://tess.elixir-europe.org/collections/rdbites-sensitive-data-collection
2	How to perform federated analysis of human cohort data	TRE User	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/materials/cineca-federated-data-analysis/
3	Developing canonical 'safe researcher' training materials for trusted research environments	TRE User	https://iassistquarterly.com/index.php/iassist/article/view/1093/1034
4	ELIXIR Webinar: Requirements in data protection law and the upcoming General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) implementation	All	https://elixir-europe.org/events/webinar-gdpr
5	EHDS Community of Practice	All	https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/eu-cooperation/health-data-access-bodies-community-practice_en?pr.efLang=pt
6	EOSC Nordic Training Hub	All	https://eosc-nordic.eu/knowledge-hub/
7	2 min explainer on Using Patient Data for Research - What is a Secure Data Environment/Trusted Research Environment?	All	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oU5UxxU5Dw
8	HUNT Cloud onboarding material and curriculum	TRE builder TRE operator	to come
9	TSD White paper	TRE builder TRE operator	https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/about/description-of-the-system.html
10	SAFE White paper	TRE builder TRE operator	to come
11	CSC user guide for sensitive data services	TRE User	https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/
12	CSC Definition of Sensitive Data	All	https://research.csc.fi/definition-of-sensitive-data
13	CREATE TRE Onboarding Process for Trusted Research Environment (TRE) by Kings College London		https://docs.er.kcl.ac.uk/CREATE/TRE/tre_onboarding/

14	UK Office for National Statistics's Safe Researcher Training		https://www.scadr.ac.uk/administrative-data/training/ons-safe-researcher-training-course-ons-srt
15	SAIL Databank Safe Researcher Training		https://saildatabank.com/safe_researcher_training/
16	Data spaces support centre		https://dssc.eu
17	FEGA onboarding guide	All	https://ega-archive.github.io/FEGA-onboarding/
18	RDMKit on the Norwegian tool assembly for sensitive data	All	https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/tsd_assembly#what-is-the-norwegian-tools-assembly-for-sensitive-data--tsd-data-management-to-ols-assembly
19	HDR UK Futures learning platform		https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/study-and-train/train/learn-with-hdr-uk-futures/
20	Training materials from anDREa MyDRE		https://support.mydre.org/portal/en/kb
21	SANE training materials		https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Working+with+sensitive+data